

Emissions from hot bitumen – Current Eurobitume activities & recommendations

Anja Sörensen^{1*}

¹ Eurobitume

*Corresponding author. Email: anja.soerensen@eurobitume.eu

ABSTRACT

Eurobitume aims to be the first reference for bitumen in Europe. We educate and promote the efficient, economic, effective, safe and sustainable use of refined bitumen. Eurobitume and its members are dedicated to safety and reliability at every stage of the handling and use of bitumen, from refining, to transportation, to delivery, and finally to use/disposal. Safe handling procedures are a vital component of this approach, ensuring that any risk to workers and members of the public is minimised.

The laws and regulations in Europe require employers to provide safe systems of work to ensure the safety of their employees and the public. Health and safety laws impose duties on all relevant stakeholders and on all involved parties to provide safe systems of work, across the entire supply chain.

Historically, measuring exposure to emissions from hot bitumen has focussed on particulate matter but has shifted over years to assessing the chemical composition of emissions. However, the interpretation of data will always depend on the methodology and test protocols applied. Temperature is the key determinant for both amount and the composition of emissions from hot bitumen. Eurobitume has recommended maximum handling and storage temperatures since at least 1997, which have been published in a number of documents.

This contribution aims to share the Eurobitume activities and knowledge on emissions from hot bitumen and recommendations and guidances on improving safe handling conditions, covering engineering measures, administrative controls, as well as personal protective equipment.

Keywords: Safety, handling, health, emissions, fume